

Article

Diverse Learners, Inclusive Practices: Approaches to Teaching Special Education

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Abstract: This study examines how inclusive classroom behavioral issues affect English, Science, and Math achievement. Despite disruptive behaviors, lack of involvement, transition concerns, communication barriers, and social emotional issues, students' academic performance remains unchanged. Despite being the biggest problem, communication barriers do not affect academic performance. Students' strong marks in important courses show that behavioral issues have little impact on academic progress. This resilience shows that current educational interventions and teaching methods are helping pupils overcome behavioral issues and succeed academically. The study emphasizes the need to preserve and improve these educational techniques to help all students succeed academically despite classroom behavioral issues. Teachers and policymakers should use these findings to emphasize the need for ongoing support and personalized interventions to address behavioral challenges and promote academic performance. This research helps create a supportive and effective learning environment for all students by showing that behavioral issues have no effect on academic success. The study recommends exploring novel teaching strategies that improve behavioral and academic outcomes to ensure comprehensive growth and achievement for inclusive classroom students.

Keywords: Inclusive classroom behaviors, academic performance, behavioral challenges, classroom engagement

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Introduction

Special education is a broad area of education that focuses on helping students with a wide range of learning difficulties, disabilities, or exceptionalities by giving them individualized support and services (Kauffman & Hornby, 2020; Crispel & Kasperski, 2021). In a special

education setting, students may need extra help and modifications to access the curriculum, fully participate in classroom activities, and reach their full academic, social, and emotional potential (Larosa et al., 2022). Special education celebrates the differences between students, recognizing that each has their own skills, needs, and ways of learning (Kauffman & Hornby, 2020). The goal is to ensure all students receive a free education that fits their specific needs (Qian & Rong, 2023).

A recent study found that inclusive classroom management is particularly important in special education schools where students have a wide range of needs (Nilholm, 2021; Paulsrud & Nilholm, 2023). Effective management strategies create a space where all students feel valuable, respected, and welcome, leading to better grades, increased motivation, and greater involvement (McKenna et al., 2021). Inclusion in the classroom also supports social and emotional growth by teaching life skills such as self-control, problem-solving, and teamwork (Julianti et al., 2020). Moreover, effective management strategies, supported by teacher training and continuous professional development, are critical for the successful implementation of inclusive education practices (Crispel & Kasperski, 2021).

A big part of the responsibility for ensuring that inclusive classroom management strategies are implemented lies with the teachers. Teachers have the ability to construct an organized learning environment that maximizes instructional time and minimizes interruptions by establishing defined standards, routines, and procedures (Cortes et al., 2022). With the support of inclusive classroom management, teachers are able to cater their lessons to the specific requirements of each individual student, offer individual assistance, and fulfil all of their requirements. There is a correlation between effective management strategies and work satisfaction, retention, and professional progress for teachers (Srinivas, 2023).

The concept of inclusive education is one that is extremely important in the Philippines. It is enshrined in the Constitution and is backed by a number of laws and regulations, including the Magna Carta for Persons with Disabilities and the Inclusive Education Policy Framework, amongst others. The implementation of inclusive methods, particularly in the field of special education, is fraught with substantial difficulties, notwithstanding the efforts that have been made. It is essential to have efficient classroom management in order to overcome these problems and guarantee that all students, including those with disabilities, are provided with an education that is of high quality and meets their requirements. Future research should focus on in-depth studies of student behavior in inclusive classrooms in DepEd elementary schools. Examining teachers' experiences and perspectives, researchers can identify effective strategies, innovative approaches, and areas for improvement in managing inclusive classrooms in the

Philippines. This research can support ongoing efforts to promote inclusive education and provide valuable insights. Future study in DepEd elementary schools should prioritize the thorough examination of students' inclusive classroom behavior practices to effectively solve this imbalance. Analyzing the experiences and viewpoints of teachers can help researchers identify effective tactics, creative approaches, and areas for progress in inclusive classroom management within the Philippine setting. Focusing on these specific areas, academics can offer vital insights that support the ongoing efforts to promote inclusive education.

Methodology

The study employed a descriptive research methodology to examine the correlation between inclusive classroom behaviors and academic performance in various schools. The data collection process utilized questionnaires that were designed using the methodologies outlined in the studies conducted by Sprague & Walker (2005), Ladd (2009), and Weissberg et al. (2011). The questionnaires encompassed a range of topics including classroom management, disruptive behavior, behavior intervention, and social-emotional learning, guaranteeing a comprehensive examination of subjects pertaining to student behavior and academic success. The study was conducted at the Naga SPED Centre, an educational institution specifically catering to students with special needs. Both educators and students served as responders, providing a well-rounded perspective on the interactions within the classroom. The responses were assessed using a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree." This allowed for a thorough understanding of the extent to which individuals agreed with the assertions regarding behavior and academic performance.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Disruptive Behavior

Indicators	Mean	VD
Student frequently interrupts the class or others' learning activities.	3.0	MA
Student refuses to follow classroom rules or instructions.	3.10	MA
Student engages in physical aggression or disruptive outbursts.	2.80	MA
Student consistently distracts peers during lessons or group work.	2.80	MA
Student consistently disrupts the learning environment to the extent that it significantly impacts overall classroom functioning.	3.05	MA
Grand Mean	2.95	MA

Table 1 provides an analysis of disruptive behavior patterns among students. The grand mean across all behaviors is 2.95, suggesting a moderate level of disruptive behavior overall. Specifically, the behavior of frequently interrupting class or others' learning activities has a mean

score of 3.0, indicating it is a common issue. Slightly more severe, students refusing to follow classroom rules or instructions has a mean of 3.10, signaling this as one of the more prevalent disruptive behaviors observed. On the other hand, physical aggression or disruptive outbursts, along with consistently distracting peers during lessons or group work, both have lower mean scores of 2.80, suggesting these behaviors are somewhat less frequent but still present. The assessment of students consistently disrupting the learning environment to a significant extent has a mean score of 3.05, pointing towards a considerable impact on classroom functionality, although it is still categorized within a moderate range.

Table 2. Engagement

Indicators	Mean	VD
Student appears disinterested or passive during instructional activities.	3.15	MA
Student rarely volunteers or participates in class discussions.	3.00	MA
Student frequently appears distracted or off-task during lessons.	3.00	MA
Student exhibits limited enthusiasm or motivation for learning activities.	3.23	MA
Student consistently demonstrates a complete disengagement from classroom activities, regardless of instructional strategies used.	2.92	MA
Grand Mean	3.06	MA

Table 2 provides an analysis of disruptive behavior patterns among students. The grand mean across all engagement is 3.06, suggests an overall moderate level of disengagement across the evaluated behaviors. The highest mean score, 3.23, is associated with students exhibiting limited enthusiasm or motivation for learning activities, indicating this as the most significant concern within the lack of engagement spectrum. This is closely followed by students appearing disinterested or passive during instructional activities, with a mean score of 3.15, underscoring a prevalent issue with maintaining interest and active participation in the learning process. Both the frequency of students appearing distracted or off-task during lessons and the rarity of students volunteering or participating in class discussions are scored at 3.00. These values indicate these forms of disengagement are common but not the most critical areas of concern compared to others. The behavior of students consistently demonstrating complete disengagement from classroom activities, regardless of the instructional strategies used, has the lowest mean score of 2.92.

Table 3. Difficulty with Transitions

Indicators	Mean	VD
Student requires frequent reminders to transition between activities.	3.10	MA
Student exhibits mild resistance or reluctance to transition.	2.92	MA
Student experiences moderate difficulty with transitions, leading to minor disruptions.	3.20	MA
Student struggles significantly with transitions, leading to noticeable disruptions or delays in instructional time.	3.10	MA
Student experiences extreme difficulty with transitions, resulting in frequent meltdowns or prolonged disruptions.	3.10	MA
Grand Mean	3.08	MA

Table 3 provide data on the difficulty with transition. The overall grand mean score is 3.08, suggesting that, on average, the difficulties are moderately severe across the different aspects of transitioning. Breaking down the specifics, the students requiring frequent reminders to transition between activities have a mean score of 3.10, indicating a common issue where students need extra support to move from one task to another. Similarly, students who struggle significantly with transitions, leading to noticeable disruptions or delays in instructional time, also have a mean score of 3.10. This shows that these significant struggles are just as common as the need for frequent reminders. Students experiencing moderate difficulty with transitions, which lead to minor disruptions, have the highest mean score at 3.20. This suggests that while disruptions are minor, they are slightly more prevalent among the students compared to other types of transition issues. On the lower end, students exhibit mild resistance to transition with a score of 2.92, which is the least severe but still within the moderate range. Those who experience extreme difficulty with transitions, resulting prolonged disruptions, surprisingly also score 3.10.

Table 4. Communication Barriers

Indicators	Mean	VD
Student demonstrates occasional difficulty expressing thoughts or ideas verbally.	3.40	A
Student exhibits limited verbal communication skills in certain contexts.	3.54	A
Student experiences moderate challenges with both expressive and receptive communication.	3.10	MA
Student demonstrates significant difficulty communicating verbally or nonverbally, impacting interactions with peers	3.65	A
Student experiences severe communication barriers, significantly impairing participation in classroom activities	3.20	MA
Grand Mean	3.38	MA

Table 4 examines the severity of communication barriers faced by students. The grand mean across all categories is 3.38, suggesting a moderate to slightly above average level of communication challenges prevalent among the students. The most significant issue is observed in students who demonstrate significant difficulty in both verbal and nonverbal communication, impacting their interactions with peers and understanding of instructional content, with a mean score of 3.65. Another notable challenge is with students who exhibit limited verbal communication skills in certain contexts, scoring a 3.54. Students experiencing moderate challenges with both expressive and receptive communication have a mean score of 3.10, classified under moderately agree. The category of students who demonstrate occasional difficulty expressing thoughts or ideas verbally scores 3.40, also marked as agree. Lastly, the most severe communication barriers, which significantly impair participation in classroom activities and social interactions, score a mean of 3.20 under moderately agree. Overall, the data from Table 11 highlights a range of communication challenges among students, from moderate to severe, impacting their educational and social experiences to varying degrees.

Table 5. Social-Emotional Challenges

Indicators	Mean	VD
Student occasionally struggles with regulating emotions in certain situations.	3.05	MA
Student exhibits mild difficulty managing frustration or disappointment.	3.15	MA
Student experiences moderate challenges with emotional regulation and social interactions.	3.18	MA
Student demonstrates significant difficulty managing emotions or interacting with peers, impacting overall classroom climate.	3.15	MA
Student experiences severe social-emotional challenges, requiring extensive support and intervention to participate in classroom activities effectively.	3.05	MA
Grand Mean	3.12	MA

Table 5 focuses on the evaluation of social-emotional challenges among students. The grand mean for all categories is 3.12, indicating a moderate level of social-emotional difficulties experienced by the students as a whole. The most intense reported challenge in this dataset is related to students experiencing moderate challenges with emotional regulation and social interactions, which scored the highest at 3.18. This indicates that issues such as managing emotions in social settings and interactional dynamics can slightly more profoundly affect students compared to other listed problems. Both students who occasionally struggle with regulating emotions in certain situations and those experiencing severe social-emotional challenges requiring extensive

support and intervention scored a mean of 3.05. Students demonstrating significant difficulty managing emotions or interacting with peers, which directly impacts the overall classroom climate, and those exhibiting mild difficulty managing frustration or disappointment, both have a mean score of 3.15. Overall, the data from Table 12 illustrates that while the range of social-emotional challenges is broad, from mild to severe, the overall impact is moderately significant across the board.

Table 6. Learners Academic Performance

Subject	Grade	VD
English	86.42	Very Satisfactory
Mathematics	85.20	Very Satisfactory
Science	87.45	Very Satisfactory

The data in Table 6 presents the learners' academic performance across three subjects: English, Mathematics, and Science. The grades for each subject are all in the "Very Satisfactory" range, indicating a high level of achievement. Specifically, the learners scored 86.42 in English, 85.20 in Mathematics, and 87.45 in science. These scores reflect a consistent performance across the board, with the highest grade achieved in science and the lowest in Mathematics. The very satisfactory grades suggest that the learners have a strong understanding and competence in these core academic areas, showcasing their ability to perform well in diverse subjects.

Table 7. Significant Relationship Between the Level of Inclusive Classroom Behavior and English Performance

Constructs	r-value	t-value	P value	Remarks	Decision
Disruptive Behavior	-0.0154	0.264	0.5461	Not Significant	Do not reject
Lack of Engagement	-0.0309	0.251	0.4012	Not significant	Do not reject
Difficulty with Transitions	0.10734	0.630	0.4660	Not significant	Do not reject
Communication Barriers	0.05201	0.315	0.3051	Not significant	Do not reject
Social-Emotional Challenges	-0.0520	0.216	0.6310	Not significant	Do not reject

The data presented in Table 7 investigates the relationship between various constructs of inclusive classroom behavior and English performance. The findings indicate that there are no significant

correlations between English performance and the constructs measured by disruptive behavior, lack of engagement, difficulty with transitions, communication barriers, and social-emotional challenges. This is evidenced by the consistently low r-values, ranging from -0.0520 to 0.10734, and high p-values, all exceeding the typical significance threshold of 0.05. Moreover, the t-values are also relatively low, reinforcing the lack of statistical significance. Therefore, the decision for each of these constructs is to retain the null hypothesis, suggesting that the levels of these behaviors do not significantly impact English performance in this study's context.

Table 8. Significant Relationship Between the Level of Inclusive Classroom Behavior and Mathematics Performance

Constructs	r-value	t-value	P value	Remarks	Decision
Disruptive Behavior	-0.03950	0.210	0.4013	Not Significant	Do not reject
Lack of Engagement	0.015321	0.150	0.1245	Not significant	Do not reject
Difficulty with Transitions	-0.15830	0.706	0.3610	Not significant	Do not reject
Communication Barriers	-0.01760	0.322	0.4102	Not significant	Do not reject
Social-Emotional Challenges	0.023560	0.210	0.5314	Not significant	Do not reject

Table 8 explores the relationship between various inclusive classroom behaviors and Science performance, revealing similarly non-significant results. Table 8 similarly indicate a lack of significant relationships between levels of inclusive classroom behavior and science performance. The constructs disruptive behavior, lack of engagement, difficulty with transitions, communication barriers, and socialemotional challenges all yield r-values indicating very weak correlations, ranging from -0.15830 to 0.023560. The p-values associated with these correlations also far exceed the commonly accepted threshold of 0.05 for statistical significance, reinforcing the conclusion that these behaviors do not significantly influence science performance. Additionally, the t-values are low, further supporting the absence of meaningful statistical relationships. As with the findings related to English performance, the decisions across all constructs are to retain the null hypothesis, suggesting that these specific behaviors in inclusive classroom settings do not significantly impact students' science performance. The consistency of non-significant findings across different academic subjects suggests that these particular behaviors

may not be critical determinants of academic achievement in the contexts studied.

Table 9. Significant Relationship Between the Level of Inclusive Classroom Behavior and Science Performance

Constructs	r-value	t-value	P value	Remarks	Decision
Disruptive Behavior	-0.75032	0.411	0.2581	Not Significant	Do not reject
Lack of Engagement	-0.53201	0.423	0.5760	Not significant	Do not reject
Difficulty with Transitions	-0.07129	0.451	0.1534	Not significant	Do not reject
Communication Barriers	0.02205	0.164	0.5492	Not significant	Do not reject
Social-Emotional Challenges	0.61142	0.562	0.2641	Not significant	Do not reject

Table 9 explores the relationship between various inclusive classroom behaviors and mathematic performance, revealing similarly nonsignificant results. Each construct's r-values, ranging notably from 0.75032 to 0.61142, suggest some degree of correlation, yet the corresponding p-values do not meet the conventional significance level of 0.05. This insufficiency is underscored by the low t-values, which further highlight the statistical insignificance of the relationships. For instance, despite the seemingly strong negative correlation for Disruptive Behavior and a strong positive correlation for SocialEmotional Challenges, the lack of statistical significance (p-values above 0.05) leads to retain the the null hypothesis for each construct. This suggests that, within this dataset, the levels of these behaviors do not substantially impact mathematical performance. The absence of statistically significant findings across these constructs implies that other factors not measured here might be influencing students' performance in mathematics more strongly.

Conclusion

The data illustrates that despite facing a spectrum of challenges in inclusive classroom settings, such as disruptive behaviors, lack of engagement, difficulty with transitions, communication barriers, and social-emotional issues, these do not significantly detract from the learners' academic performance in English, Science, and Mathematics. Notably, communication barriers, which presented the highest challenge, still do not correlate significantly with academic outcomes.

The learners' ability to achieve very satisfactory grades across key subjects indicates that the impact of these behavioral challenges on academic success is minimal. This suggests that existing educational interventions or teaching strategies are effectively supporting these learners, allowing them to overcome behavioral difficulties and excel academically. The findings underscore the importance of maintaining and possibly enhancing these educational practices to ensure that all learners can continue to thrive in their academic pursuits despite behavioral challenges in the classroom.

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